

Empowering Adolescents through Academic Resilience: A Literature - Based Perspective

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Abstract

Students in the adolescent phase undergo rapid changes at their emotional, physical, and social levels, which for one reason or another are not acceptable to every adolescent. The extra pressure of scoring well in academics, being active in social platforms, and showing total engagement in family and society is not welcomed by most adolescents. Good performance in academics paves the way for reputed jobs which leads to a settled life. There are students who possess the ability to overcome failures in a positive manner, and there are also students who lack the coping skills to overcome the adversities of life. So, there is an urgent need to teach the students about the skill of overcoming barriers in their academic settings, which is known as academic resilience. In the present paper, the researcher tries to study academic resilience of adolescent students across the globe. The paper helps in understanding the need to develop academic resilience among adolescent students and its relationship with teachers, parents, society, peer group, internet use, and the overall well-being of a student. For the present study, the researcher collected 14 articles from various online resources like ERIC, Google Scholar, Shodhganga, Research Gate, etc. This review will help many educators, researchers, and policymakers to prepare proper and effective intervention programmes to foster academic resilience among school-going children.

Keywords: Academic Resilience, Adolescents, Academic Settings.

Introduction:

Since human civilization came into existence, the world has witnessed various advancements and technological upgrades. The development in any sector occurs through the process of transformation and adaptive changes. One of the sectors that has been consistently upgraded and transformed according to society is the educational sector. In the age of technology and social media, the educational sector is becoming more and more dynamic. With the advancement of technology, the lives of students, especially of the adolescent group, have been entirely changed from what they were decades ago. To mention specifically, it can be said that the students who are in their adolescent phase are deeply affected by the changing pattern of our education system.

Adolescence is a transformative phase of human life that is characterized by rapid changes within an individual at the physical, mental, emotional, and social levels. This is a very tender age where a child develops a sense of self-awareness and self-consciousness, and hence, it is to be dealt with carefully. Ahangarnasab and Yoo (2023) stated that the magnitude of adolescents' experience varies based on biological and psychosocial factors, and so do the levels of behavioural problems.

During the adolescent phase, a child has to make career choices, perform well in school, and manage social pressures, which often leads to stress and anxiety. In such a complex environment where an adolescent is very much affected by the increasing academic demands and societal pressure, there is a

need to develop within him a behaviour or quality that helps him overcome all these obstacles easily. This ability of an individual to cope up with academic setbacks and thrive successfully in their academic settings is known as academic resilience.

In the current scenario, where many adolescents experience physical and mental health issues due to rising academic competition, academic resilience will act as a protective factor, helping students to stay focused and bounce back from academic failures. Cassidy (2015) stated that academic resilience encompasses an effective solution while dealing with educational challenges, by reducing the effect of risk factors (e.g., stressful academic life events) and strengthening protective factors (e.g., active coping mechanisms, social support, and positive approach) that enhance the ability to deal with such challenges.

Academic Resilience:

Resilience is the determination of a person that gives them the strength to cope with all types of challenges, obstacles, and hardships coming in their way to a successful life. Garnezy and Masten (1991) identify resilience as a significant process of adaptation, which entails capacity enhancement. Although human beings face struggles in every phase of their lives, during the adolescent stage, the need for resilience increases due to academic and societal pressure. Wang et al (1994) argue that academic resilience plays a significant role in enhancing the chances of success of an individual's academic journey, thereby minimizing the influence of socio-economic and other challenges. Apart from academics, academic resilience has been identified to play a positive and influential role in defining the success pathway while undertaking different professional and personal tasks (Radhamani & Kalaivani, 2021). Academic resilience is the characteristic trait of an individual that helps in overcoming chronic difficulties in academic settings. (Romano et al, 2021). It also helps students in adapting to academic demands (assignments and exams) and maintaining a positive outlook, even though going through difficult times. Academic resilience provides a suggestive solution to address psycho-social and socio-economic challenges leading to improvised performance in academics. Indeed, academic resilience and its variations serve as a platform to measure who stays for how long in the academia (Rao & Krishnamurthy, 2018). Alva (1991) stated that resilient students are those who perform well by keeping themselves motivated even when they are facing the difficult times or situations in their life. Hence, it can be said that academic resilience is one of the important aspects of educational settings and must be promoted in institutions.

Review of Literature:

Rao and Krishnamurthy (2018) analysed the effect of academic resilience on the educational attainment of high school students in their study. For this purpose, the teenage students studying in the public school of North Bangalore and belonging to economically disadvantaged background were chosen as a sample. This study was carried out by using Bharatiyar University Resilience Scale (BURS) and David's Battery of Differential Abilities (DBDA—revised version 32) to measure the resilience parameters and scholastic performance of the students, respectively. Moreover, the study used marks scored in the internal tests in various subjects as secondary data. The two variables used in the study were subjected to Pearson's product-moment coefficient test, and the use of mean, standard deviation, t-test, and Analysis of Variance were done for the data analysis. It finds the existence of a significant correlation between the level of resilience and the scholastic performance of students. The outcomes stated that with reference to resilience attributes and scholastic abilities no significant difference existed within gender and that the early adolescents were less resilient in comparison to late adolescents.

Pinki and Duhan (2020) conducted a study to determine relationship of academic resilience with mental health of adolescent students. The research centred on 200 adolescents belonging to rural and urban areas of Hisar district of Haryana state. For the fulfilment of the objectives of the study, the researcher utilized Academic Resilience Scale by Mallick and Kaur (2015) and Mental Health Inventory by Jagdish and Shrivastava (1983) to evaluate academic resilience and mental health of the participants, respectively. The analysed data revealed that male respondents had higher academic resilience and better mental health than the female respondents. In fact, urban respondents showed better mental health as compared to the rural respondents.

Jaladdin and Masli (2021) investigated the link of emotional intelligence with resilience of secondary school students in the Klang Valley Area. The researcher chose 100 students through a probability (random) sampling technique and employed the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) and the Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSREIT) for data collection. Analysis of data was done using various statistical techniques such as frequency, standard deviation, mean, percentage, Pearson correlation, and t-test. From the results, it was concluded that students maintained an average level of resilience and emotional intelligence; and also no significant difference existed regarding these variables with respect to gender, school location and streams. Further, the outcomes revealed that there was a significant relationship of resilience with emotional intelligence.

Nandal et. al.(2021) conducted a study on a sample of 652 participants to witness the correlation between resilience and academic achievement of students from deprived sections (Scheduled Caste) studying in higher secondary. For the purpose, a resilience scale was developed, and the performance of students in their respective examinations (Percentage scored) served as one of the measurement indicators. The statistical techniques used for analysing the collected data were: t-test and Pearson product-moment coefficient. The findings established a significant relationship between resilience and gender.

Romano, et., al (2021) evaluated the association between academic resilience, perceived teacher emotional support and school engagement. For this study, 205 teenage students (14-19 yrs) studying in high schools of Italy were selected as a sample by a convenient sampling method. The self-report questionnaire on academic resilience, the perceived teacher emotional support scale, and the school engagement scale were used as the tools or instruments for the collection of data. For analysing the data, descriptive statistics such as kurtosis and skewness were performed along with the use of Pearson correlation. The data suggested that academic resilience as well as the perceived teacher emotional support were related to school engagement, and both were associated with each other. Also, it was found out that teacher emotional support acted as a mediator between school engagement and academic resilience.

Turan (2021) examined the contribution of academic resilience in life satisfaction and social- emotional learning competencies of teenagers. The research was conducted on 371 adolescents through structural equation modelling and utilized the measurement tools, namely, Adolescents' Social and Emotional Learning Scale developed by Totan (2018), Satisfaction with Life Scale developed by Diener et al.(1985), and the Academic Resilience Scale developed by Martin and Marsh (2006). The findings revealed that SEL competencies were significant predictors of both academic resilience and life satisfaction. The study suggested that integrating academic resilience into SEL programs could enhance students' happiness and overall quality of life.

Xie and Kue (2021) conveniently selected 172 students of eighth grade studying in schools of Guiyang (China) to investigate the linkages of resilience, academic emotions and achievement. The sample included nearly fifty percent of the females. Researchers used the adolescents' academic emotions questionnaire and the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale to measure students' academic emotions and resilience, respectively. From results, it was concluded that the relationship of resilience and academic achievement of students were affected by the higher level of positive academic emotions.

Rasheed and Sultan (2023) explored the academic resilience of 140 randomly selected secondary school students (70 male and 70 female) by conducting a descriptive study. The selected respondents studied in class 10th in Eidgah zone of district Srinagar, Jammu and Kashmir. The study employed the academic resilience scale developed by Dr. Mihir Kumar Mallick and Ms. Simranjit Kaur and assessed the compiled data by applying appropriate inferential and descriptive statistics t-test, mean, percentage and standard deviation. The study finds a higher resilience among the female students compared with their male counterparts.

Afzali, Hosseinian, and Nooripour (2024) explored the mediating role of academic competence in the relationship between perceived teaching style and academic resilience among adolescents. This descriptive correlational study involved 400 high school students from Tehran, selected through random sampling. The Academic Resilience Inventory (ARI), developed by Samuel in 2004, Teacher as Social Context (TASC), and the Academic Competence Evaluation Scale (ACES), developed in 1999,

were utilized as a measurement tool for the study. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and correlation matrix, along with inferential statistics through path analysis. Based on the results, it was concluded that there was a significant relationship between academic competence, teaching style, and academic resilience. Furthermore, teaching styles characterized by support and involvement were found to have a direct and substantial impact on academic competence, which in turn positively influenced academic resilience.

Latifian et. al.(2024) studied the impact of academic resilience and internet addiction on the mental health of high school students studying in Tehran(Iran). The researcher for the study opted descriptive survey method, in which 758 high school students of Tehran, academic year 2022-2023, were taken as a sample. The research tools employed for this study were: Samuel's Academic Resilience Inventory, Young's Internet Addiction Test and Goldberg's Mental Health Questionnaire. The multiple regression analysis and Pearson's correlation calculated the relationship between variables. Calculation and tabulation of kurtosis, skewness, standard deviation and mean of the variables were also done. Analysis of the data exhibited the inverse role of extreme use of internet on the mental status of the students and also depicting that students having higher levels of academic resilience have good mental health. From the results, it was also interpreted that academic resilience and internet addiction were negatively associated with each other.

Shengyao et. al. (2024) conducted a study to determine how parenting methods of the adolescents is related to the academic resilience. The study also deals with the mediating roles of academic motivation and self-efficacy. As a sample, a total of 518 students were chosen through a random sampling process from educational institutions in the Chinese provinces, and more than 60% of respondents were over 25 years old. The key statistical tools that were used for this investigation included path and mediation analysis. The findings of the study highlighted the fact that parenting methods and academic resilience had a direct and positive relation to each other. The results emphasized that the intermedator elements play a major role rather than having direct impact of parenting styles.

Ali and Kumar (2025) made an attempt through their study to understand the academic resilience of the students of secondary level studying in Belpukur (West Bengal). The researchers for their study utilized the standardized academic resilience scale developed by Munmi and Yeasmin in 2023 to collect data. The study was conducted on 146 students chosen through the purposive sampling method, and the data were analysed by mean, S.D, percentage, and t test. Results showed no significant difference between male students and female students regarding their academic resilience and it also demonstrated that maximum of secondary school male students possessed low level of academic resilience. It was also found that the maximum secondary school female students possessed an average level of academic resilience, and there was no significant difference in the level of academic resilience in relation to gender.

Kumar (2025) did a comparative study of Academic resilience with the test anxiety of students of intermediate education. The sample of the study consisted of 680 higher secondary students studying in the schools of Dindigul district, selected through a stratified random sampling technique. The Academic Resilience Scale, developed and validated by Nalini Rao (1998), and the Test Anxiety Inventory, developed and validated by Richard Driscoll, were used as measurement tools for the study. The researchers employed percentage analysis, t-test, ANOVA, and Karl Pearson Product-Moment Correlation for data analysis. The findings of the study indicated that academic resilience and test anxiety were statistically different with regard to gender, and a statistical difference existed among boys, girls, and co-education school students of intermediate education about academic resilience and test anxiety. In addition, a statistical relationship was observed between test anxiety and academic resilience of students of intermediate education, whereas rural and urban locale students of intermediate education showed no statistical difference regarding their test anxiety.

Panda (2025) in his descriptive survey study compared the academic resilience of rural and urban secondary school students in the North 24 Parganas District of West Bengal, India. The study included a sample of 112 students from Classes IX and X, selected through simple random sampling from four different schools. Academic resilience of the students was measured by using the academic resilience

scale (ARS-30), which was developed by Cassidy (2016). The findings of the study revealed that urban students showed significantly higher levels of academic resilience than rural students.

Discussion:

The findings of the reviewed literature illustrate an influential role of academic resilience in defining various aspects of adolescents' lives, especially their mental health and academic performance. The outcomes of the reviewed studies demonstrate a strong relationship between academic resilience and mental well-being. Adolescents with higher academic resilience showed good mental health and could face the adversities of their academic life positively. This adaptability is very much necessary in today's fast moving life where the school going adolescents have to make quick choices regarding their career. The results emerged out to show a positive correlation between academic resilience and the scholastic achievement. Furthermore, a noticeable difference was evident regarding gender and locality where some studies concluded showing male students exhibiting higher academic resilience and better mental health as compared to females, whereas others resulted in showing higher academic resilience among female students. Locality wise, urban adolescent students demonstrated higher level of academic resilience and mental health when compared to their rural counterparts.

Researches showed a positive linkage between teacher emotional support, social emotional learning (SEL) competencies and the academic resilience. These studies suggested that the level of satisfaction and engagement of an adolescent student enhances when a supportive educational environment is provided to them. The role of teaching styles and parenting style in fostering academic resilience is also highlighted. It is indicated that parents and teachers play a major role in promoting self-efficacy and motivation among adolescents.

Literature also provided clear evidence of the negative association between higher time spent on the internet and the mental well-being of adolescents, thus determining resilience to be a protective factor. Overall, academic resilience comes out to be a factor which is shaped by an individual, his family members and his institution. Therefore, the schools and institutions should focus on academic building programs and strategies, which will help learners to thrive successfully amidst adversity. These interventions can be done through counselling sessions and must be inclusive in nature considering the gender, socio economic background and cultural context.

Conclusion:

Academic resilience is a fundamental element in determining the psychological well-being and overall academic success of a student. All those adolescents who are resilient in nature, easily come out of academic setbacks, parental, societal and peer pressure. They are also good in maintaining their emotional health along with keeping themselves motivated. As we advance in technology and social media, the need to become a resilient student itself becomes a necessity, to avoid all kinds of distractions. The researches have proved and indicated the need for practicing resilience training by the secondary schools. It will be a successful venture only when it empowers the teachers, engages the parents and develop student centred support systems. It is to be noted that by fostering academic resilience programs the school will not only get positive outcomes but will help its students to easily cope up with the unwanted and adverse situations.

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization- Ms. Krishna Chauhan

Writing- Original Draft Preparation and Review – Ms. Krishna Chauhan

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